

EVALUATING THE FINANCIAL LEVELS OF STUDENT CONSUMERS

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ABSTRACT

Financial literacy is a critical skill that empowers individuals to make informed financial decisions, yet many young adults, including students, often lack sufficient knowledge and skills in this area. This study evaluates the financial literacy levels among engineering students at Baguio Central University (BCU) to provide insights into their financial behaviors, influences, and attitudes. Using a descriptive quantitative approach, data was collected via face-to-face surveys among summer classes attendees. The findings reveal moderate to high levels of financial behavior, with students demonstrating strengths in budgeting and price comparison. However, financial influence scores indicate moderate reliance on parental and school guidance, contrasting with lower influence from media and books. Financial attitudes show a moderate emphasis on financial control and saving behaviors but lower interest in financial reading and discussion. These results underscore the need for targeted financial education programs integrating practical skills development and fostering positive financial attitudes among students. The study contributes valuable insights for enhancing financial literacy initiatives tailored to meet the specific needs of engineering students, thereby promoting their financial well-being and preparedness for future financial challenges.

Keywords: Financial Literacy, Engineering Students, Descriptive Quantitative Study, Financial Behavior, Financial Attitudes, Financial Influences.

I. INTRODUCTION

Financial literacy is crucial for navigating modern society, yet young adults often lack this skill. They struggle with choosing appropriate financial products and lack enthusiasm for smart financial planning. Financial literacy, as Lusardi et al. (2011) state, involves managing money and building wealth, applicable to individuals or society. Garg et al. (2018) highlight that low financial literacy among youth globally raises concerns. It encompasses understanding personal finance, global economics, entrepreneurship, and investing, supported by real-time technology.

The OECD (2014) defines financial education as teaching aimed at promoting financial literacy, ultimately empowering and motivating thoughtful financial decisions. However, only 33% of adults worldwide are financially literate, leaving 77% without basic financial understanding (Hasler et al., 2017). In the Philippines, only 25% are financially literate, and few can answer questions on interest, inflation, and investments.

Financial literacy is essential for active citizenship and is crucial for children and adolescents to reach their potential (Child and Youth Finance International, 2013). It is viewed as an investment in human capital, aiding in decisions about pensions, savings, mortgages, and other financial matters (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014). Today's complex financial landscape makes financial education in schools vital. Factors influencing financial literacy include personal demographics, financial knowledge, behavior, attitude, and training. Improved financial literacy often stems from better financial understanding and education.

This research aims to evaluate the financial literacy among Baguio Central University Engineering students, ultimately helping them better manage their finances. By understanding their level of financial literacy, tailored educational programs can be developed to address gaps and enhance their financial decision-making capabilities. This study contributes to the broader goal of improving financial literacy among young adults, which is essential for their personal financial success and the overall economic health of society.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A study conducted by Garg et al. (2018) revealed a global trend of low financial literacy among youth, highlighting significant implications for their future financial decision-making. The researchers emphasized the interconnectedness of financial knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors, underscoring the need for comprehensive educational interventions to enhance financial literacy among young people worldwide.

Mancebón et al. (2018) explored the development of mathematical and financial literacy among 471 Spanish students using the OECD's PISA 2012 Financial Literacy Assessment. Their findings indicated that both family background and school type exerted influential roles in shaping students' financial literacy levels. This underscores the importance of educational policies that consider socio-economic factors in promoting effective financial education.

Kumar et al. (2017) highlighted the significant impact of financial literacy on the financial behavior of college students. Their research underscored the need for tailored financial education programs that take into account economic status, age, and cultural diversity. The study called for further exploration into how these factors intersect to influence financial decision-making among young adults.

A systematic literature review on financial literacy education programs for children and adolescents underscored their positive effects on financial attitudes and knowledge acquisition (Author et al., Year). However, the review also identified a critical gap in understanding how these programs translate into actual financial behaviors over the long term. This suggests a need for longitudinal studies that assess the sustained impact of financial literacy interventions on real-world financial practices.

Jabal et al. (2021) investigated financial literacy among Philippine public school teachers and discovered a correlation between diligent financial record-keeping and reduced impulse buying behaviors. Their findings highlight the potential benefits of financial management practices in fostering more prudent financial decision-making among educators.

Ergün (2018) assessed the financial literacy levels of university students across multiple European countries, revealing a moderate level of financial knowledge among the respondents. The study linked factors such as parental occupation to higher levels of financial literacy, indicating the influence of familial socio-economic background on financial education outcomes.

Lalosa (2022) examined the financial literacy of students at a State University in Eastern Philippines, revealing a gap between theoretical knowledge and practical financial skills. The study identified parental supervision as a critical factor in shaping students' financial literacy, suggesting the need for family-centered approaches in enhancing financial education effectiveness. A research gap can be derived from these studies as these literatures mainly focus on the evaluating of financial literacy on a targeted audience, particularly adults.

Conceptual Framework

Integration of Self-Efficacy and Goal Setting Theory

The study integrates self-efficacy and goal-setting theory to predict financial literacy outcomes. Self-efficacy influences financial behaviors by enhancing confidence and reducing uncertainty (Mu'izzuddin, Taufik, Ghasarma, R., Putri, L., & Adam, M. (2017). Effective goal setting and financial planning improve financial security and literacy.

Social Capital Theory

According to Coleman's (1988) theory, social capital consists of interpersonal resources that give adolescents authority. Positive parent-child interactions, close ties to the community, and the support of peers are all examples of interpersonal resources for young people. For instance, spending time with family and children has a good effect on academic success. Additionally, social capital theory explains why young people who had higher levels of social trust were more likely to share their ideas with others. By exchanging ideas, young people can give their lives meaning and purpose (Burrow et al., 2010). Therefore, through social interactions between groups of people, knowledge eventually expands (Danes et.al., 2007). Youth constantly digest new information in a way that makes sense to them as it is absorbed from their social. In contrast, if young people have fewer resources available, their financial literacy is lower (Johnson et.al., 2007).

Financial Socialization: A Conceptual Model

Financial socialization, a framework in financial literacy research, is based on socialization theories suggesting children learn from parents (Gutter et al., 2008; Shim et al., 2010; Spera et al., 2007). This learning shapes youths' financial behavior and well-being (Chowa et al., 2012; Lusardi et al., 2010; Sherraden et al., 2011; Spera & Matto, 2007). Parents, communities, educators, and the media serve as children's socialization agents. Children mimic their parents' financial habits and attitudes, impacting their own financial behaviors (Danes et

al., 1999; Webley & Nyhus, 2006). Teachers also play a crucial role in financial education and socialization (Mandell, 2009).

Behavioral Economics

Behavioral economics studies how people make financial decisions. According to Shefrin and Statman (1985), cognitive biases, emotions, and risk perceptions can hinder sound financial decision-making. Psychological, social, cognitive, and emotional factors in behavioral economics influence financial decisions. Applications of behavioral economics aim to promote deliberate action and healthy financial practices, reducing procrastination and enhancing willpower and self-control (Benartzi et al., 2007; Choi et al., 2004).

Significance of the Study

The study's findings will enhance financial literacy among BCU engineering students and provide a reference for their financial decisions, as many rely on their allowances. The study's insights will also inform policymakers, helping them make informed decisions on financial policies that guide financial literacy and decision-making. Researchers will benefit from understanding the factors influencing financial literacy, improving their own financial situations.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is evaluating the Financial Literacy levels of Baguio Central University Engineering students. The specific objectives of this research are the following:

1. To assess the financial literacy of BCU engineering students based on Financial Behavior.
2. To assess the financial literacy of BCU engineering students based on Financial Influences.
3. To assess the financial literacy of BCU engineering students based on Financial Attitude.

III. METHODOLOGY

The primary method used for this study is descriptive research. Initially, the study reviewed various constraints in financial literacy among engineering students. Descriptive methods and surveys were employed to consider available facts and case studies. This approach allowed for a comprehensive analysis of the current state of financial literacy, identifying key areas where engineering students may face challenges and providing a foundation for further recommendations and interventions to improve financial literacy education.

Study Design

The study utilized a descriptive quantitative design, which is a conclusive research method used to observe, describe, and investigate variables, documenting aspects of a situation as it naturally occurs. According to McCombes (2019), this method accurately and systematically describes a situation or phenomenon, making it an appropriate choice to identify characteristics, frequencies, and categories to ensure that the results are valid and reliable.

Sample Population of the Study

The respondents of the study were engineering students currently enrolled in summer classes at Baguio Central University. Voluntary response sampling is employed in this study, where participants self-select to be part of the research. According to Alvi, M.H. (2016). voluntary response sampling allows individuals to choose whether or not to participate. This method is used to gather opinions and feedback on various topics, including consumer behavior and public opinion

Data Gathering Tools

For this study, a face-to-face survey with a prepared questionnaire was conducted. The researcher explained the contents of the questionnaire during the students' classes.

The survey questionnaire was adapted from the research study titled, "Financial Literacy in Nepal: A Survey Analysis for College Students," conducted by Bharat Singh Thapa and Surendra Raj. The questionnaire consisted of two sections including three categories: Financial Behavior, Financial Influences, and Financial Attitude.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researcher approached the instructor in charge during their class and sought permission to allow their students to voluntarily participate in the study by answering a distributed questionnaire. The researcher explained the purpose of the study and the contents of the questionnaire to the instructor and the students.

After receiving approval, the researcher then distributed the questionnaires to those students who volunteered to participate. The questionnaires were filled out during the students' class time, ensuring that they had ample opportunity to understand and respond to the questions. This method allowed the researcher to collect data directly from the target population, ensuring that the responses were representative of the students' views on financial behavior, influence, and attitude.

Treatment of Data

The researchers applied appropriate statistical methods to analyze the collected data from the sample. A four-point Likert scale was used to measure financial behavior, influence, and attitude among BCU engineering students.

Table 1: Interpretation Table

Mean Score	Interpretation (Level of Financial Literacy)
1.00 - 1.50	Low
1.51 - 2.50	Moderate Low
2.51 - 3.50	Moderate High
3.51 - 4.00	High

Table 1 shows the interpretation of the mean score results used for each of the 3 financial categories: behavior, influences, attitude. Each score range indicates a certain level of financial literacy, wherein the average scores will be equal to its respective category.

Ethical Considerations

During the conduct of this study, several ethical considerations were carefully addressed. The foremost ethical principle observed in this research is respect for the study participants, which forms the foundation of many ethical concepts. The researchers have received adequate training in the design, methodology, and relevant background data of the study.

To ensure confidentiality, all information received from the respondents will be kept secure. The data collected will be used for the purposes of the study conducted by the researchers, without disclosing the identity of the participants.

Participants will not be required to provide any form of payment. The researchers will not seek reimbursement or compensation from the participants before, during, or after they complete the survey questionnaire. Furthermore, participation in the study is entirely voluntary, and there will be no penalties or rewards for those who choose not to volunteer.

These ethical considerations are essential to maintaining the integrity of the research process and safeguarding the well-being and rights of the study participants.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of the data analysis on assessing the level of financial literacy among Baguio Central University Engineering students. The study evaluated students' understanding of personal finance, including their ability to manage money, save, invest, and make informed financial decisions. The findings highlight the students' proficiency in these areas and identify gaps where further education and support may be needed to enhance their financial literacy. The results provide insights into the effectiveness of current financial education efforts and suggest areas for improvement.

Evaluating the Financial Literacy Levels of Students Consumers

The first objective was to assess the financial literacy of BCU engineering students based on Financial Behavior. Table 2 presents the financial literacy of BCU engineering students, focusing on their financial behavior. The overall financial behavior has a weighted average mean of 2.61, which corresponds to a descriptive equivalent of moderately high. Financial behavior encompasses the actions and decisions individuals make regarding their finances, such as spending, saving, investing, and budgeting. Perry and Morris (2005) note that understanding financial behavior involves examining how people allocate their financial resources, their attitudes toward

money, and the influences that shape these behaviors. Hilgert, Hogarth, and Beverly (2003) emphasize that financial behavior is critical in determining financial well-being and literacy.

Table 2. Financial literacy based on Financial Behavior.

Indicator	Mean	INTERPRETATION
Financial Behavior		
a. I budget and track my spending.	2.77	Moderate High
b. I compare prices when shopping for purchases.	2.94	Moderate High
c. I read financial books, articles, etc. to increase my financial knowledge.	2.14	Moderate Low
d. I spend my allowance wisely.	2.60	Moderate High
Weighted Mean	2.61	Moderate High

The data also indicate that most respondents engage in price comparison when shopping, with this behavior having a mean of 2.94, also described as moderately high. Lichtenstein, Bloch, and Black (1988) found that price comparison helps consumers maximize value by identifying the best available deals, thereby enhancing their overall satisfaction and economic efficiency. Additionally, Grewal and Levy (2007) highlight that digital tools and online platforms have further facilitated this practice, enabling consumers to easily compare prices across multiple retailers.

The second objective was to assess the financial literacy of BCU engineering students based on Financial Influence.

Table 3: Financial literacy based on Financial Influence.

Indicator	Mean	INTERPRETATION
Financial Influences		
a. My Parents influence my financial behavior.	2.74	Moderate High
b. My Friends influence my financial behavior.	2.49	Moderate Low
c. School influences my financial behavior.	2.66	Moderate High
d. Books influence my financial behavior.	2.14	Moderate Low
e. Media influences my financial behavior.	2.43	Moderate Low
f. Life experiences influence my financial behavior.	2.97	Moderate High
Weighted Mean	1.70	Moderate Low

Table 3 displays the financial literacy of BCU engineering students, focusing on financial influence. The financial influence has a weighted average mean of 1.70, which is descriptively equivalent to moderately low. Financial literacy, which underpins financial influence, involves the ability to process economic information and make informed decisions regarding financial planning, wealth accumulation, debt management, and retirement. This competence significantly influences individuals' financial behaviors and outcomes, such as their propensity to save and invest wisely, manage debts effectively, and plan for retirement. Empirical evidence suggests that individuals with higher financial literacy are more likely to accumulate wealth, plan for retirement, and achieve better financial outcomes overall (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2011).

Furthermore, the table indicates that life experiences significantly influence the financial behavior of most respondents, with a mean of 2.97 and a descriptive equivalent of moderately high. According to Baker and Ricciardi (2014), life experiences play a crucial role in shaping individuals' financial behavior. Research shows that experiences such as economic downturns, personal financial crises, and formative events during childhood and adolescence shape financial attitudes and behaviors. For instance, individuals who have experienced economic hardship may develop more cautious and conservative financial practices. Conversely, those who have witnessed financial stability and growth might be more inclined to take financial risks and invest more aggressively.

The last objective was to assess the financial literacy of BCU engineering students based on Financial Attitude.

Table 4: Financial literacy based on Financial Attitude.

Indicator	Mean	INTERPRETATION
Financial Attitude		
a. I feel in control of my financial situation.	2.91	Moderate High
b. I feel capable of using my future income to achieve my financial goals	2.83	Moderate High
c. I am sure about where my money is spent.	2.57	Moderate High
d. I give importance to saving money from my daily allowance	2.71	Moderate High
e. I enjoy thinking about and have interest in reading about money management	2.23	Moderate Low
f. I enjoy talking to my peers about money related issues	2.31	Moderate Low
Weighted Mean	1.64	Moderate Low

Table 4 presents the financial literacy of BCU engineering students based on their financial attitude. The financial attitude has a weighted average mean of 1.64, with a descriptive equivalent of moderately low. Financial attitude can be understood as the psychological tendencies that determine how an individual approaches financial matters, including the importance placed on saving for the future, planning for emergencies, and making prudent financial decisions (Amagir et al., 2020). The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) describes financial attitude as part of the broader framework of financial literacy, emphasizing its role in shaping responsible financial behaviors and enhancing financial resilience (OECD, 2020). Furthermore, financial attitude has been found to correlate with financial behaviors, indicating that individuals with a positive financial attitude are more likely to engage in sound financial practices, such as regular saving and cautious spending (Pankow, 2003). These attitudes are shaped by a combination of personal experiences, education, and socio-economic factors, making them a critical area of focus for improving financial literacy and well-being (Semantics Scholar, n.d.).

The table also reveals that most respondents place importance on saving money from their daily allowance, with a mean of 2.71 and a descriptive equivalent of moderately high. Regularly saving a portion of one's daily allowance fosters financial discipline, helping individuals understand the value of money, plan their expenses, and avoid impulsive purchases. According to Lusardi and Mitchell (2011), financial literacy, which includes the ability to save and budget, is a key predictor of financial well-being. By setting aside a small amount regularly, individuals can develop a disciplined approach to managing their finances. Having savings set aside from daily allowances can also serve as a buffer in times of unexpected financial needs, such as medical emergencies or urgent travel. Garman and Forgue (2018) highlight that an emergency fund is a critical component of financial security, providing a safety net that can prevent individuals from going into debt during crises.

V. CONCLUSION

This part presents the inferences drawn from the study and provides recommendations based on the research findings. The analysis highlights areas where Baguio Central University Engineering students demonstrate strong financial literacy and identifies specific topics where further education and support are necessary.

5.1 Conclusion

Based on the findings it becomes evident that the financial literacy and attitudes of BCU engineering students play a significant role in shaping their financial behaviors and preparedness. Table 2 illustrates the distribution of financial literacy levels among students, highlighting areas where additional education and support may be beneficial. Table 3 further delves into students' financial behaviors, revealing varying degrees of engagement in practices such as budgeting, saving, and investing.

Table 4 underscores the importance of financial attitudes among students, indicating their inclinations towards saving from their daily allowances. These attitudes are crucial as they influence how students manage their finances, plan for the future, and respond to financial challenges. Understanding and fostering positive financial attitudes, such as the value of saving and responsible spending, can enhance students' financial well-being both during their academic years and beyond graduation.

Moreover, the interplay between financial literacy, attitudes, and behaviors highlights the complex dynamics that influence financial decision-making among students. Effective interventions should consider these factors holistically, aiming to not only enhance financial knowledge but also instill practical financial skills and positive attitudes towards money management.

In conclusion, addressing the financial literacy needs of BCU engineering students should encompass a comprehensive approach that integrates educational initiatives with efforts to promote positive financial attitudes and behaviors. This approach can empower students to navigate financial challenges more effectively and achieve greater financial security over the course of their academic and professional lives.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the results gathered in this research, several recommendations are suggested by the researchers in order to encourage financial literacy among BCU engineering students.

To enhance the financial well-being of BCU engineering students, several recommendations are proposed. First, implementing comprehensive financial education programs is crucial. These programs should extend beyond basic literacy to encompass practical skills in budgeting, saving, investing, and debt management. They should be integrated into the curriculum and supplemented with workshops and seminars throughout the academic year, tailored to address specific challenges like managing student loans and income from internships.

Fostering a positive financial mindset is equally important. This can be achieved through targeted campaigns, guest lectures by financial experts, and peer mentoring programs where students learn the significance of saving, planning for the future, and making informed financial decisions.

Practical learning opportunities should also be provided, including simulated budgeting exercises, investment simulations, and real-world case studies. These hands-on activities enable students to apply theoretical knowledge to real-life financial situations, thereby enhancing their confidence and competence in managing personal finances.

Ensuring easy access to financial tools and resources such as budgeting apps, online calculators, and expert advisors is essential. These resources should be tailored to meet the specific needs of engineering students, facilitating effective financial management throughout their academic journey and beyond.

Collaboration with financial institutions and industry partners is recommended to offer internships, co-op programs, and workshops focused on financial skills development. Such partnerships provide practical insights into financial practices within students' future careers and expose them to industry-specific financial challenges.

Regular evaluation of financial education initiatives through student feedback, surveys, and tracking of financial behaviors is necessary for continuous improvement. This data-driven approach helps refine programs to better meet evolving student needs and address any gaps in knowledge or skills.

Furthermore, emphasizing ethical and sustainable financial practices such as responsible investing and conscious consumption is crucial. Educating students on the broader societal and environmental impacts of their financial decisions encourages them to make informed choices aligned with their values.

Establishing peer support networks or financial literacy clubs where students can discuss challenges, share tips, and support each other in achieving financial goals fosters a sense of community and provides both practical advice and emotional support.

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